

INTRODUCTION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF NON-GOVERNMENTAL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: The modern world level of development of information and communication technologies is such that the creation of a national system in the country in accordance with the integration of the infrastructure of the global information space and the national information network is an important factor in the effectiveness of national economy, management, science and education. These problems are quite complex and at the same time relevant for our republic. The results of the current economic, structural and other changes will depend on how and when the problems of informatization in the country will be resolved.

Key words: dictionary, literature, development, language, subject, e-learning.

The creation of e-learning tools in academic disciplines will further expand the use of modern information and communication technologies in the teaching of these disciplines. This, in turn, is a key factor in deepening students' knowledge of these disciplines, increasing the quality and effectiveness of education.

The implementation of such efforts will further accelerate the widespread use of modern pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process, provide teachers with advanced pedagogical knowledge and equipping them with technologies, improving their skills, in-depth study of the experience of foreign higher education institutions and the introduction of effective methods and tools in our national education system.

Multimedia is a rapidly evolving modern information technology. Its distinguishing features include:

- Integrates different types of information: traditional (text, tables, decorations, etc.), original (speech, music, video clips, TV footage, animation, etc.), into one software product. Such integration includes various devices for recording and displaying information,
- Work at a given time, unlike text and graphics, which by nature are static, audio and video signals are considered only at certain intervals of time. Fast mobility of the central processor for processing and displaying video and audio information on the computer, the capacity of the data transmission bus RAM and video memory, large capacity external memory, volume and the speed of exchange on the computer input-output channels is about two required to be doubled,
- A new level of "human-computer" interactive communication, in which the user receives a much wider and more comprehensive information in the process of communication, which allows to improve the conditions of education, work or leisure.
- Educating students and retraining on the basis of multimedia tools is a topical issue today. The concept of multimedia came into our lives in the early 90s. The question is, what is it? Many experts have different interpretations of this term. In our view, multimedia is an integrated way of delivering educational materials to students based on audio, video text, graphics and animation effects based on software and hardware of computer science.
- In developed countries, the method of teaching is currently used in the field of education. In fact, not every family can afford to have fun without multimedia. The total turnover of multimedia in 1981 was \$ 4 billion, and in 1994 it was \$ 16 billion. And not every computer on sale today is complete without multimedia. Efforts to use computers extensively in education in the 1970s were thwarted, primarily because of their extremely low productivity. Practice shows that multimedia-based teaching is twice as effective and time-saving. Multimedia-based learning can save up to 30% of time, and the knowledge gained will be stored in memory for a long time. If students accept the given material on the basis of construction, the retention

of information will increase by 25-30%. In addition, if the training materials are presented in a combination of audio, video and graphics, the retention of materials will increase by 75%.

- Teaching students through multimedia has the following advantages:
- a) deeper and more complete assimilation of the given materials there is a possibility;
 - b) the desire to work closely with new areas of learning further increases;
 - c) the opportunity to save time as a result of reduced study time to achieve;
 - g) when the acquired knowledge is stored in a person's memory for a long time and is needed can be applied in practice.

Methodology of building information support of management processes with any objects on the basis of computer information systems as a fundamental science of computer science and information technology is engaged in the development of There is also the idea that one of the main tasks of science is to determine what information systems are, what their place is, what structure they should have, how they work, what laws are specific to it. In the field of informatics in Europe, the following main scientific directions can be distinguished: network design, computer integrated process production, economic and medical informatics, social insurance and environmental informatics, professional information systems.

The advent of the multimedia system has led to revolutionary changes in many professional fields, such as education, science, art, computer training, advertising, technology, medicine, mathematics, business, and scientific research.

Although the idea of using computers in the education system appeared long ago, the use of information technology in all areas of the education system was fully realized with the advent of computers equipped with multimedia devices. began to be put into practice.

The use of multimedia in education allows:

- Ensuring the humanization of education;
- increase the efficiency of the educational process;

- development of personal qualities of the learner (mastery, thirst for knowledge, independent learning, self-education, ability to self-improvement, creative abilities, applying the acquired knowledge in practice acquisition, interest in learning, attitude to work);
- developing students' communicative and social skills;
- The opportunities for individualization and differentiation of open and distance education will be significantly expanded through the use of computers and information e-learning resources for individual education;
- look at the learner as an active learner, recognizing his or her value;
- take into account the personal experience and individual characteristics of the student;
- Carrying out independent learning activities, in which the learner learns and develops independently;
- Develop in learners the skills to use modern educational technologies to help them adapt to today's rapidly changing social conditions in order to successfully carry out their professional tasks.

The process of implementing person-centered learning using multimedia tools requires the development and use of modern, multidisciplinary, subject-oriented multimedia learning tools. They include an extensive database, a knowledge base in the field of education, artificial intelligence systems, expert-training systems, and laboratory practices with the ability to create mathematical models of the processes and events being studied.

Multimedia is useful and productive due to its ability to take into account the individual characteristics of learners and help increase their interest (motivation), as well as the combination of different types of multimedia educational information, interactivity, flexibility. lim technology.

Ensuring interactivity is an important achievement of digital multimedia compared to other means of presenting information. Interactivity involves providing relevant information according to the needs of the learner. Interactivity allows you

to manage the presentation of information to a certain extent: learners can individually change the settings set in the program, study the results, respond to the program request about a specific request of the user, set the speed of submission and number of repetitions possible.

But there are a few things to keep in mind when using multimedia. Multimedia learning materials need to be easy to understand, up-to-date, and accessible.

In order to fully explore the full potential of multimedia technologies and use them effectively, learners will need the support of a competent teacher.

As with the use of textbooks, the use of multimedia means that the learning strategy is to enrich the content of the learning process only when the teacher is engaged not only in providing information but also in assisting, supporting and managing the process. possible. Typically, presentations enriched with beautiful images or animations are more appealing than plain-looking texts, and they can provide the necessary emotional level by complementing the material presented.

Multimedia tools can be used in a variety of educational styles can be understood and used by individuals with different mental and age characteristics of learning and acquisition of knowledge: some learners through direct reading, some through listening comprehension, and others through (video) They like to learn and acquire knowledge through research.

Interactive multimedia technologies provide extraordinary convenience to the learner with academic needs. In particular, it promotes the development of phonological and reading skills in learners with hearing impairments, as well as their visual assimilation of information. In the case of speech and physical disabilities, it is possible to use the tools based on their individual needs.

Multimedia is an effective and promising teaching tool that provides the teacher with a wider range of information than a traditional source of information; visual and use not only text, graphics, diagrams, but also sound, animations, videos, etc. in combination; allows students to select the types of information in sequence according to their level of perception and logical study.

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